

LEGAL BASIS OF ORGANIZING THE ELECTRONIC GOVERNMENT SYSTEM IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. This article analyzes the legal basis of creating an electronic government system in the Republic of Uzbekistan. The main attention is focused on the analysis of legal documents, including the decisions of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan and other legal documents regulating the issues of digitization of public services and the development of information and communication technologies in public administration. Also, the research highlights the main directions of development of electronic government in Uzbekistan and measures to improve the efficiency of using electronic systems in the state apparatus.

Key words: electronic government, legal framework, Republic of Uzbekistan, digitization, administrative government, electronic systems

Many countries are trying to introduce e-government in order to increase the efficiency of public administration and provide citizens with the opportunity to use public services electronically in the process of the development of information technologies and the digitization of society. In the Republic of Uzbekistan, the "Electronic Government" system based on the relevant legal documents is being actively implemented. Analysis of legal documents, including decisions of the President of Uzbekistan and other regulatory documents, is an important step in understanding the legal basis of creating an electronic government system in our country. From this point of view, a number of legal documents and regulatory legal documents aimed at regulating issues of digitalization of public services and development of information and communication technologies in public administration are being adopted. [5].

The decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated August 22, 2022 "On measures to further improve the mechanisms of introducing information and communication technologies into the activities of state bodies" is one of the important documents. In this decision, specific measures and directions for the development of the "Electronic Government" system are

defined, and the need to strengthen the use of information and communication technologies in public administration is indicated. [1].

Also, the measures of the Cabinet of Ministers dated July 16, 2020 No. 444 "Further development of the electronic government system, as well as the introduction of the procedure for electronic reporting of the activities of state bodies and organizations to the public The decision on" is also important [2].

In addition, the Law "On State Services" and the Decision "On Measures to Improve the Organization of State Services in Electronic Form" and other laws and regulatory documents regulate the digitization of state services. is important in comparison [3].

These documents define the main directions of development of electronic government in our country, including digitization of public services, development of information and communication technologies, and creation of an electronic management system. In addition, measures such as personnel training, infrastructure improvement, and development of standards were determined by them to improve the efficiency of the use of electronic systems in the state apparatus. Consequently, the legal framework plays an important role in the creation and development of the electronic government system in the Republic of Uzbekistan, and in ensuring the stability, transparency and efficiency of public administration in the digital age.

In conclusion, it can be noted that the legal basis for creating an electronic government system in the Republic of Uzbekistan is an important tool for regulating and facilitating the process of digitalization of public administration. Presidential decrees, laws and regulatory legal documents create the legal basis for the development of the "Electronic Government" system and provide the appropriate institutional basis for its operation.

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